

Study on Physico chemical properties and Nutritional properties of selected ragi and bajra grains

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Abstract

The present investigation aimed to analyze the physico chemical characteristics and nutritional properties of selected ragi and bajra grains. It encompassed assessing properties like 1000 grain weight, dimensional properties, Arithmetic mean diameter, porosity, bulk density, true density, and angle of repose, alongside determining moisture content, protein, fat, carbohydrates, and ash content. The findings revealed that ragi (ATL 1 variety) contained 10.5% moisture, 67.56% carbohydrates, 7.21% protein and 3.14% ash had highest nutritional profile when compared to ragi (traditional variety) while bajra (CO 9 hybrid) exhibited 61.16 % carbohydrates, 10.98 % protein, and 2.04 % ash had better nutritional profile when compared bajra (traditional variety). These results hold significance for equipment designers and processors, aiding them in developing processing machinery tailored to grain qualities, thereby enhancing overall processing efficiency. Understanding these physical and functional properties is crucial for facilitating the development of new food products.

Key words

Ragi, Bajra, Physical parameters, color value, proximate composition

Introduction

Millets have great importance for food and nutrition security among increasing agricultural costs, climate change and growing mouths to feed world population. Millets are highly nutritious, they have various health benefits, require very less costs for cultivation and are able to tolerate biotic and abiotic stresses (Bandyopadhyay *et al.* 17). Millets are small-seeded grasses that are hardy and grow well in dry zones as rain-fed crops, under marginal conditions of soil fertility and moisture, grown throughout the world that belong to the family Poaceae of the monocotyledon group. As per the FAOSTAT, global millet production for the year 2016 was 30.35 million tons. Indian millet production is ~10 million tons and in the small millet production is 467 thousand tons (Himanshu *et al.* 18).

Millets are unique because of their richness in calcium, dietary fibre, polyphenols, carbohydrates (70-80%) and protein (9-14%). It is a gluten-free cereal and also rich in phytochemicals which help to lower cholesterol level and reduced cancer risk due to its phytate content (Shadang and Jaganathan 14). Millets are commonly categorized into major millets, including sorghum and pearl millet, and minor millets, such as finger millet, barnyard millet, little millet, kodo millet, foxtail millet, and proso millet. While global millet consumption experienced a decline of 0.9% in recent years, it is projected to exhibit positive growth from 2019 to 2024. Forecasts indicate a significant rise in the millets market, with its value expected to increase from over \$9 billion to surpass \$12 billion by 2025. This growth is attributed to favorable governmental policies aimed at expanding the global millets market throughout the period spanning 2019 to 2025. (Eduro *et al.* 21)

Millets are highly nutritious grains that offer various health benefits. They are non-glutinous and non-acidic, making them easy to digest. Millets provide a rich source of energy, proteins, fatty acids, vitamins, minerals, dietary fiber, and polyphenols. While millet proteins lack certain essential amino acids like lysine and threonine, they are abundant in sulfur-containing amino acids such as methionine and cysteine. Additionally, millets are abundant in phytochemicals, micronutrients, and antioxidants like phenolic acids and glycosylated flavonoids, contributing to their nutritional value (Shah *et al.* 21).

Millet grains play a significant role in India's food grain economy, constituting approximately one-sixth of the total food grain production. The production of millets is primarily concentrated in South and East Asia (60%), followed by Eurasia and Central Asia (14%), Africa (16%), and the remaining world regions (10%). India stands as the leading producer of millet grains, contributing to around 33-37% of the global production of 28 million tonnes. Among minor millets produced in India, finger millet accounts for approximately 81%, with the remainder produced by kodo millet, foxtail millet, and little millet. (Kumar *et al.* 24).

Finger millet (*Eleusine coracana*), commonly known as 'ragi', holds a significant position in Indian cuisine and is typically consumed without de-hulling. India stands as the primary producer of finger millet, contributing approximately 60% of the global production. Characterized by its tiny grain with a dark brown seed coat, finger millet boasts higher polyphenol levels compared to other continental cereals like barley, rice, maize, and wheat. Its nutritional value has garnered increasing attention due to its rich dietary and functional fiber content, starch composition, as well as notable levels of calcium and iron. Various finger millet varieties have been documented to

contain calcium levels ranging from 220 to 450 units and iron levels between 3% to 20%. Finger millet (FM) grains exhibit a variety of shapes, sizes, and colors, with brown being the predominant color. (Lokur *et al.* 23)

Pearl millet (*Pennisetum glaucum*) ranks as the sixth most significant cereal globally. In regions like India and Africa, pearl millet grains are primarily utilized for food consumption. As a vital nutriceal, it serves as a staple food for rural communities. Pearl millet stands out as a notable source of proteins, minerals, and fibers. (Takhellambam *et al.*16). Pearl millet (*Pennisetum glaucum*) serves as a versatile cereal crop cultivated for various purposes including food and feed for centuries particularly in African and Asian nation. Its resilience to drought and high temperatures enhances its suitability for regions where other cereal crops like wheat and maize struggle to thrive. Pearl millet covers over 29 million hectares of land globally, with its primary cultivation concentrated mainly in Africa and Asia, where it is the largest producer. Developing countries contribute over 95% of pearl millet production, with India emerging as the leading producer. (Rathore *et al.* 16).

Physical characteristics of cereal grains encompass parameters such as moisture content, 1000-sample weight, bulk density, true density, porosity, aspect ratio, and sample shape. Although India stands as one of the largest producers of millets globally, there remains a lack of comprehensive data on the physical properties of ragi and bajra grains, with limited studies in Asian nations like India. Understanding these physical and functional properties is crucial for facilitating the development of new products (Sreenatha *et al.* 23). The aim of this study is to determine Physical properties, colour value and proximate composition of the selected ragi and bajra grains.

Materials and methods

Procurement of raw materials

Ragi (Traditional variety) and bajra (Traditional variety) was procured from the local farmers Madurai district of Tamil Nadu, India. Ragi (ATL 1 variety) was procured from the Centre of Excellence in Millets, Athiyanthal, Tiruvannamalai District, Tamil Nadu, India, bajra (CO 9 Hybrid) was procured from the Department of Millets, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore. The proposed research work was carried out in the Department of Food Science and Nutrition, Community Science College and Research Institute, Madurai. The selected millets were cleaned, sorted and used for the study. All the estimations were carried out in triplicates.

Physical Properties

Different physical properties such as thousand grain weight, porosity, true density, bulk density, angle of repose were determined using standard procedures.

Dimensional properties

Ten seeds were selected randomly from selected ragi and bajra for the study. The grains were analyzed for three distinct dimensional properties (mm) - length (L), width (W), and thickness (T). A vernier digital calliper was employed to measure these properties with an accuracy of 0.01 mm.

Arithmetic mean diameter

Arithmetic mean diameter was calculated from the dimensional values using the following equation.

$$(Da) = L \times W \times T / 3$$

where

L- Length

W- Width

T- Thickness

Equation from the Arithmetic mean diameter using the method of (Mpotokwane *et al.* 8).

Thousand grain weight

One hundred grains were randomly selected from different lots of samples and weighed using an electronic balance (accurate to 0.01g) at a specified moisture content. The sample weight was then multiplied by 10 to determine the average thousand grain weight. (Tavakoli *et al.* 10).

Bulk Density

Bulk density, measured in kilograms per cubic meter (kg/m^3), represents the relationship between the mass of the sample and its overall volume. To determine it, a 500 mL cylinder was filled with grains, and the bulk density was computed by dividing the sample weight by the volume of the cylinder, as specified in the equation. (Karababa and Coşkuner 2013)

$$\text{Bulk Density (Bp)} = \text{Sample weight} / \text{Volume}$$

True Density

The True density (measured in kg/m^3) was calculated using the liquid displacement technique with a top-loading balance. 100 grams of grains were submerged in a graduated beaker filled with distilled water. The volume of water displaced was measured using the method described in (Karababa and Coşkuner 2013).

$$\text{True Density} = \frac{\text{Sample weight}}{\text{Initial volume} - \text{Final Volume}}$$

Porosity

Porosity, expressed as a percentage, represents the proportion of empty space within the bulk grain that is not filled by the grains themselves, as defined by (Sangamithra *et al.* 16). This value was determined by employing an equation based on both the true density and bulk density, utilizing the approach outlined by (Sangamithra *et al.*16)

$$\text{Porosity}(\varepsilon) = \frac{P_t - P_b}{P_t} \times 100$$

where ε =porosity, p_t =true density and p_b = bulk density

Angle of repose

The angle of repose was derived from observations of the natural formation of heaps composed of food grains and powdered food items, as detailed in Pradhan *et al.*'s study from 12.

$$\text{Angle of repose}(\Theta) = \tan^{-1} \frac{2h}{D}$$

Where Θ = angle of repose in degrees

h = height of the circular plate and

D = diameter of the circular plate

Colour values

The L^* values indicates lightness/darkness and it extended from 0 black to 100 (white). The a^* and b^* value indicated sample colour dimension, a^* value indicate redness (+a) to greenness (-a) while b^* value indicate yellowness (+b) to blueness (-b) larger a^* value corresponded more redness and larger b^* value corresponds more yellowness. (Pradhan *et al.* 12).

Proximate composition

Proximate Analysis

Moisture content, fat, protein, total carbohydrate and ash were analyzed in the selected Ragi (Traditional and ATL 1 variety) and bajra (Traditional and CO 9 Hybrid variety). All the determinations were done in triplicate and the results were expressed as the mean value.

Moisture content

Moisture content was assessed using the AOAC (2005) method as outlined below:

$$\% \text{ Moisture content} = \frac{\text{Loss in weight}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times 100$$

Fat

The crude fat content of the sample was determined using the Soxhlet apparatus method ×

$$\% \text{ Crude fat} = \frac{\text{Weight of dried ether soluble material}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times 100$$

Protein

The protein content was assessed according to the (AOAC 5) method. The percentage of nitrogen and subsequently protein was calculated using the following equation:

$$\% \text{ Nitrogen} = \frac{\text{TS} - \text{TB} \times \text{Normality of acid} \times 0.014}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times 100$$

Where, TS = Titre volume of the sample (ml)

TB = Titre volume of Blank (ml),

0.014 = Meq.wt. of N₂

% Protein = Nitrogen × 6.25

Carbohydrate content

The total carbohydrate content of the samples was determined using the phenol sulfuric acid method specified in (AOAC 5). This involved calculating total carbohydrate by difference, subtracting the measured protein, fat, ash, and moisture from 100.

Ash

The sample was dried at 100°C and charred on an electric heater, followed by ashing in a muffle furnace at 550°C for 5 hours, in accordance with (AOAC 5) guidelines. The calculation was performed using the provided formula.

$$\% \text{ Ash content} = \frac{\text{AW}}{\text{IW}} \times 100$$

Where , AW= Weight of Ash

IW = Initial weight of dry matter

Colour properties of millet grains

The colour of the grains has been documented using three distinct components, namely, color L*, color a*, and color b*. The parameter L* represents brightness, with the intensity of color for L* ranging from 0 (representing black) to 100 (representing white); whereas a* signifies the presence of red tones and b* indicates the presence of yellow tones. The various numerical values corresponding to the color attributes of millet grains can be observed in Table 4.

Result and Discussion

Physical properties of selected Finger millet and pearl millet

Different physical properties such as length, width, thickness, Arithmetic mean diameter, Geometric mean diameter, thousand grain weight, bulk density, true density, porosity, angle of repose, colour value (L*a*b) were determined and results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Physical properties of selected ragi and bajra grains

Parameters	Ragi (Traditional variety)	Ragi (ATL 1 variety)	Bajra (Traditional variety)	Bajra (CO 9 Hybrid variety)
Length(mm)	2.28±0.02	2.34±0.56	9.45±0.36	9.50±0.47
Width(mm)	1.54±0.56	1.56±0.97	1.87±0.67	1.90±0.96
Thickness(mm)	1.24±0.21	1.26±0.53	2.66±0.89	2.68±0.58
Arithmetic mean diameter(mm)	1.45±0.67	1.53±0.87	15.66±0.95	16.12±0.87
Thousand grain weight(g)	502.21±0.25	504.78±0.42	642.12±0.67	647.36±0.26
Bulk Density(kg/m ³)	995.5±0.76	998.52±0.86	802.12±0.48	805.16±0.78
True Density(kg/m ³)	1516.2±0.91	1534.6±0.23	1293.31±0.37	1295.12±0.34
Porosity(%)	32.43±0.57	33.67±0.67	39.68±0.65	40.24±0.56
Angle of repose(%)	21±0.87	22±0.48	28±0.78	29±0.67

*Each value is mean of three determinations

Physical properties play a crucial role in various stages of processing and enhancement of value, encompassing parameters like thousand kernel weights, porosity, bulk density, True density, and angle of repose, among others. Understanding the physical characteristics of grains and seeds is crucial when developing equipment for handling, transportation, storage, and processing.

The size, shape and density play a significant role in the segregation mechanisms observed on oscillating chafers and gravity tables. The True density and porosity are fundamental characteristics in the advancement of ventilation and desiccation frameworks due to their impact on the impediment to air circulation within a stockpile, while the inclination angle of repose heap holds great significance in the design of apparatuses for material flow and storage facilities. The data illustrated in Table 1 exhibited distinct physical characteristics of finger millet, and pearl millet grains. The findings derived for various attributes including Length(mm), Width(mm), Thickness(mm), Arithmetic mean diameter(mm), Geometric mean diameter(mm), Thousand grain weight(g), Bulk Density(kg/m³), True Density(kg/m³), Porosity(%) and Angle of repose(%) represent the mean values obtained from three determinations.

The ragi and bajra showed thousand grain weight ranging from (502.21- 647.36) g the lowest for ragi grains and highest for bajra grains. The values for length, width and thickness for ragi (traditional variety), ragi (ATL 1 variety), bajra (traditional variety) and bajra (CO 9 Hybrid variety) showed were 2.28, 1.54 & 1.24mm; 2.34, 1.56 & 1.26mm ; 9.45, 1.87 & 2.66mm and 9.50, 1.90 & 2.68mm respectively. The average arithmetic mean diameters were 1.45,1.53, 15.66 and 16.12 mm respectively for ragi (traditional variety), ragi (ATL 1 variety), bajra (traditional

variety) and bajra (CO 9 Hybrid variety) in order. The values obtained were in agreement with (Swami & Swami 10) who reported similar values for millet grains.

Bulk densities of for ragi (traditional variety), ragi (ATL 1 variety), bajra (traditional variety) and bajra (CO 9 Hybrid variety) were 995.5, 998.52, 802.12 & 805.16 g/cm³ respectively. True density of bajra (Traditional variety) was found to be 1293.31g/cm³ which is least among all the grains whereas the ragi (traditional variety), ragi (ATL 1 variety) and bajra (CO 9 Hybrid variety) had 1516.2, 1534.6, 1293.31 and 1295.12 respectively. The ragi (Traditional variety) 32.43% least porosity among all millet grains whereas ragi (ATL 1 variety), bajra (traditional variety) and bajra (CO 9 Hybrid variety) had 33.67, 39.68 and 40.24 % porosity respectively. The ragi (Traditional variety) 21 % least angle of repose among all millet grains whereas ragi (ATL 1 variety), bajra (traditional variety) and bajra (CO 9 Hybrid variety) had 22, 28 and 29 % porosity respectively. The obtained results were comparable with (Mercy and Kiruba 21).

Colour value

Bajra exhibited the lightest colour, followed by ragi grains. The L* values denoting colours were 64.69, 64.72, 39.54 and 40.12 for Bajra traditional variety, bajra CO 9 Hybrid variety, Ragi traditional variety and Ragi ATL 1 variety. Based on the a* values shown in the table it can be noted that Ragi (ATL 1 variety) had high intensity towards red colour 4.15 followed by Ragi (Traditional variety) at 4.02. Bajra (CO 9 Hybrid variety) at 3.7, Bajra (Traditional variety) at 3.5. The amount of redness was highest in ragi (Traditional variety) as compared to all other millet grains. The b* values was denotes yellowness which was highest in bajra CO 9 Hybrid variety followed by Bajra traditional variety (8.9), Ragi ATL1 variety (6.54) and Ragi Traditional variety (6.49). The results obtained demonstrated similarities with the findings of previous studies conducted by (Badau *et al.* 2) and (Arya 8), which focused on investigating the physical characteristics of pearl millet, finger millet, and foxtail millet, respectively.

Table 2 Colour values of selected ragi and bajra grains

Millet grains	L*	a*	b*
Ragi			
Ragi (Traditional variety)	39.54	4.02	6.49
Ragi (ATL 1 Variety)	40.12	4.15	6.54
Bajra			
Bajra (Traditional Variety)	64.69	3.5	8.9
Bajra (CO 9 Hybrid variety)	64.72	3.7	9.1

*Each value is mean of three determinations

Chemical properties

Different chemical properties such as moisture, fat, carbohydrates, protein, and ash was examined, and the findings are presented in Table 3.

Table 3 Proximate composition of selected ragi and bajra grains

Nutrients(%)	Ragi (Traditional variety)	Ragi (ATL 1 variety)	Bajra (Traditional variety)	Bajra (CO 9 Hybrid variety)
Moisture	10.7	10.5	12.3	12.01
Carbohydrates	65.23	67.56	60.99	61.16
Protein	7.15	7.21	10.92	10.98
Fat	1.94	1.91	5.28	5.32
Ash	3.12	3.14	2.01	2.04

*Each value is mean of three determinations

The moisture content in selected millets grains were 10.7, 10.5, 12.3 and 12.01 % in ragi (traditional variety), ragi (ATL 1 variety), bajra (traditional variety) and bajra (CO 9 Hybrid variety) respectively. The carbohydrates in selected millets grains were 65.23, 67.56, 60.99 and 61.16 % in ragi (traditional variety), ragi (ATL 1 variety), bajra (traditional variety) and bajra (CO 9 Hybrid variety) respectively. The values for fat, protein, Ash for ragi (traditional variety), ragi (ATL 1 variety), bajra (traditional variety) and bajra (CO 9 Hybrid variety) were 1.94, 7.15 & 3.12%; 1.91, 7.21 & 3.14%; 5.28, 10.92 & 2.01% and 5.32, 10.98 & 2.04 % respectively.

Similar results were obtained by (Kumar *et al.*16). Similar results were reported by (Maharishi *et al.* 21) for bajra (Nithyashree 19) for ragi.

Conclusion

Overall, it can be inferred that the significance of investigating physical characteristics is deemed fundamental data in the development of machinery and equipment utilized in both the harvesting process and subsequent post-harvest activities, including storage operations. The relevance of these characteristics in determining the dimensions of the machinery, especially in terms of separation, transfer, and sorting apparatus, is noteworthy. Ultimately, the findings suggest that pearl millet and finger millet are rich in nutrients, rendering them potentially valuable in the enhancement and diversification of food products. These millet grains are processed into flours for the preparation of various items such as porridge, puddings, pancakes, biscuits, roti, bread, and other snacks.

AUTHOR'S CONTRIBUTION

Conceptualization of research (ST, AS); Contribution of materials (ST, AS, VR, GM, PK, VS); Analysis of data and Interpretation (ST, PK); Preparation of Manuscript ((ST, AS, VR, GM, PK, VS).

DECLARATION

All authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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